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CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

Deliverable 4.5: Lessons learnt from the application to the three case studies (pilots)

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
AE	Acoustic Emission System
CO2	Carbon Dioxide
DT	Digital Twin
FBG	Fiber Bragg Grating
FOS	Fiber Optic Sensors
FR	France
GM	Governance Model
GRU	Gated Recurrent Units
LL	Living Lab
LSTNet	Long Short-Term Net
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
IT	Italy
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
NOx	Nitrogen Oxides
PL	Poland
PM	Particulate Matter
POD	Probability of Detection
SB	Smart Buoy

SCMS	Synchromodal Corridor Management System
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
SIR	Subsurface Inspection Radar
VNF	Voies Navigables de France

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1. Executive Summary

Deliverable 4.5 documents the lessons learnt from applying CRISTAL technologies and the Living Lab (LL) governance framework across three pilot corridors—France, Italy, and Poland. Its relevance to the project lies in translating real-world pilot experience into actionable guidance for future large-scale deployment of CRISTAL innovations. By systematically analysing technological performance, governance arrangements, and stakeholder dynamics, this deliverable serves as a bridge between the project’s technical developments and their practical, long-term integration into European inland-waterway systems. It thereby contributes directly to the project’s objective of enabling climate-resilient, digitally supported, and operationally reliable transport infrastructure.

The deliverable represents a core output of Work Package 4 and feeds into several overarching project results:

- the validation of governance and business models for digital corridor management,
- the assessment of technology–system fit across diverse institutional contexts, and
- the formulation of a generic implementation plan to support future replication.

Its findings inform future WP10 activities and provide essential input for upscaling strategies beyond the pilot phase.

This deliverable is jointly developed by the University of Antwerp (lead), SOGESCA, Unioncamere/Uniontransporti, ENEA, Fraunhofer, Infrastrutture Venete, the University of Gdańsk, and the three infrastructure managers VNF (France), AIPo/IV (Italy), and Polish external partners including VAN Cargo S.A.

The analysis across France, Italy, and Poland reveals that the successful deployment of CRISTAL technologies depends on six interlocking conditions: (1) strong and structured data availability, (2) incremental bottom-up deployment, (3) integration with existing operational systems, (4) continuous stakeholder-driven refinement, (5) institutional anchoring, and (6) parallel governance reform.

Key results include:

- **Technological validation:** SCMS, DT, AE, FOS, Smart Buoys, and SIR all demonstrated relevance, though maturity varied by context.
- **Pilot-specific insights:** France emphasized system integration and data harmonization; Italy highlighted the centrality of governance renewal; Poland exposed the critical need for hydrological monitoring and infrastructure modernization.
- **Governance findings:** Strong leadership, clear mandates, and stakeholder mapping significantly improve innovation uptake.
- **Cross-context lessons:** Digital tools amplify value only when operational readiness, data foundations, and governance coherence co-evolve.

Overall, Deliverable 4.5 shows that CRISTAL’s innovations hold substantial promise for improving the reliability, resilience, and sustainability of inland-waterway transport. Realizing this potential requires coordinated investment in digital systems, governance and policy reform, and stakeholder cooperation. When combined, these elements create the conditions for Europe to advance toward a modernized, climate-resilient inland-waterway network.

1.1. Introduction

Deliverable 4.5 will go into the practical insights gained from the pilots. Table 1 specifies exactly which technologies were tested in each location. A distinction has been made between the two material states of the technology. The first family comprises digital innovations; the second consists of physical sub-systems that could theoretically operate as stand-alone applications but, in practice, feed data to the SCMS. Because these physical devices generate raw information that must be processed and visualised to become actionable knowledge, their connection to the SCMS is essential. Not every technology has been fully implemented and tested in real time during the project; several solutions have been developed and validated in the laboratory, indicated with an “O”, while the applications trialed under real operating conditions are marked with an “X”. Even so, every component is treated as part of the SCMS scope and of the wider governance framework.

Table 1: Technologies and innovations created, implemented, and tested in the CRISTAL project, source: Cristal D4.2

		Innovation	France	Poland	Italy
Digital innovations	a	Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)	O	O	O
	b	Digital Twin (DT)	O	O	O
Developed PHYSICAL submodels	1	Intelligent/Smart Buoy System (I/SBS)		X	
	2	Acoustic Emission (AE) Technology	X		X
	3	Fiber Optic Sensors (FOS)			O
	4	Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) of engineered infrastructures Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) Technology	X		

The deliverable’s purpose is to translate the pilot specific experiences into information that can guide policy makers, infrastructure managers, and other logistics stakeholders. Building on the governance framework defined in WP4 and the technology packages developed in WP2 and operationalised through the corridor management plan of WP3, this deliverable analyses the effectiveness of the living-lab governance and business models adopted in each pilot, assess the implementation plans followed in the pilots, and formulate the lessons learnt for each specific pilot as well as more generally.

The analysis uses three sources of evidence. First, it draws on technical CRISTAL outputs, including the detailed technical documentation of WP2, the deliverables of WP3, and that of WP4, which sets out technology and pilot-specific business and governance models. Second, it uses the observations logged by the pilot teams and the living labs. Third, it incorporates the results of a dedicated cross-pilot workshop held in June 2025, during which pilot leaders told us about lessons already learnt, unexpected success stories, challenges encountered, expectations for the coming months and the risks that could threaten final outcomes using a set of Miro boards (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Example of the MIRO board used for the workshop

1.2. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The document is organised in six sections. Section 2 presents the insights from the French pilot, Section 3 examines the Italian experience, and Section 4 reviews the Polish activities. Section 5 brings the findings together, identifies the lessons that are transferable across contexts and proposes a generic set of lessons. Lastly, Section 6 summarises the main conclusions and reflects on good practices and difficulties encountered when preparing this deliverable.

By turning concrete, site-specific observations into broadly applicable insight, Deliverable 4.5 provides a bridge between the technical innovations developed in CRISTAL and the future large-scale deployment of these or other technologies along Europe's inland-waterway corridors and beyond.

2. Lessons learnt from the French pilot

Within the French pilot, the different technologies were piloted with different insights and results. These will be discussed below. Table 2 and Table 3 summarise the technologies used and tested within the French pilot.

CEDRE, a technology developed by VNF, links the transport management systems of freight operators directly to the VNF system so that cargo declarations enter the Electronic Reporting International Notification Message (ERINOT) format automatically. ERINOT is used for the reporting of voyage-related information for both dangerous and non-dangerous cargo carried on-board by vessels sailing on inland waterways (European Union, 2010). The first transporter has already connected successfully, and a second one is onboarding. Solutions for the costs are under investigation to improve the attractiveness to other stakeholders. The data generated by CEDRE are, by cutting administrative effort, encouraging a modal shift toward inland waterways while providing more reliable information for route optimisation, fee calculation and infrastructure planning.

Fluv'IOTe, another technology created by VNF, applies cameras and artificial-intelligence analysis to geolocate barges that are not equipped with AIS transponders and to indicate mooring occupancy. Initial tracker trials preceded CRISTAL. In 2023 camera-based tests began, and during 2024 image outputs were cross-checked with AIS data. Additional machine-learning work is still required, and quay-occupancy results are not yet disseminated to users, but the tool already raises safety and reliability by detecting vessels that are out of place.

Smart Buoys (SBs) equipped with GPS were installed on the Moselle to support flood management. The first field tests revealed excessive movement alerts, and the chosen mitigation reduced battery life which caused the buoys to switch off. Because the devices do not yet satisfy VNF technical criteria, further research and development is needed and no operational impact has been achieved so far.

Sub-surface Inspection Radar (SIR) was applied at Amfreville lock. The equipment identified zones of interest but could not yet specify their nature; distinguishing between voids, different concretes or water pockets will require additional machine-learning refinement. Even in its present form the tool helps target where invasive inspections should be carried out, allowing infrastructure managers to prioritise limited resources.

Within the Corridor Management component, the SCMS alert system is operational and was seen as highly attractive for users. The re-routing function remains constrained by the absence of reliable railway-capacity data and the observatory is not yet connected to the Digital Twin. Users therefore benefit mainly from the alerts, while the re-routing module is considered useful but raises concern that cargo leaving the waterway might not return. The Digital-Twin framework for locks and buoys has been created, but predictive capability is limited because the necessary data sets have not yet been collected and local teams still need additional training. Acoustic-Emission monitoring detects micro-cracks without human presence, though no diagnostic results for the inspected lock are available yet and predictive maintenance will depend on a larger reference database.

Table 2: Technologies in French pilot – part 1, source: Cristal D8.2

Technology	Use	Results	Impacts
CEDRE	Create a new system to collect freight data to optimize loading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology selected: directly link transporters TMS to VNF system • The selected technology has been tested and works with one stakeholder. • Another stakeholder is currently implementing it, for the rest a solution is researched to handle the cost • The data gathered is currently translated into ERINOT format to share it with all infrastructure managers • The toll freight is currently reframed in line with the current reality IWT sector 	<p>On modal shift (indirect effect):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impactful: the main French transporters are implementing it as it reduces administrative costs of using IWW • Creates more reliable data for optimizing routes and transport infrastructures, as well as for calculating fees
Fluv'IOTe	Use of IoT for the purposes of navigation facilitation and safety: barge geolocation thanks to cameras and AI analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First, tests were performed with trackers on barges prior to CRISTAL • Second, tests with a camera and AI were performed in 2023 • Third, the use of second test images was crossed with AIS data during 2024, the system allows to geolocate barges not equipped with AIS and inform about mooring occupancy • More machine learning is needed for the AI and information about quay occupancy is not yet shared with IWW users (could be part of a further project) 	<p>On IWW reliability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impactful: increase safety on IWW detecting vessels and shipment out of place due • The dissemination of quay availability information would ensure more reliability in freight shipping schedule and optimize staff time
Smart Buoys	Flood management on	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buoys were tested in real environment. They were 	Targeted: maintenance efficiency and IWW reliability

	the Moselle River: use of smart buoys equipped with GPS	<p>turned in smart buoys by the installation of lights with a GPS on it. First, the alerts of movement were to frequent, to tackle that issue, the solution found increased the battery consumption, turning off the buoys</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This system does not meet VNF technical criteria, and further R&D needs to be done to decrease the energy consumption of the device 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As the technology is not adapted to IWW yet, it has no impact
Subsurface Inspection Radar	Test inspection radar tool on the Moselle to improve infrastructure maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SIR has been tested on Amfreville lock. On the tested zones, the technologies evidence Figures of Interests, but it does not evidence what it is (it could be a different type of concrete, a void, water, sand, etc.). To be more precise on that aspect, the technology needs more machine learning. Further tests will be performed on Moselle corridor 	<p>Impact on Maintenance efficiency:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Even with these limitations, the technology could help target where to perform invasive inspection and optimize the limited resources of infrastructure managers

Table 3: Technologies in French pilot – part 2, source: Cristal D8.2

Technology group	Use	Technology	Results	Impacts
Corridor Management	Use of SCMS, DT, and AE	Synchromodal Corridor Management System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The alert system is working Re-routing system works but lacks data from railway The observatory works but is not yet connected to the DT lacking data 	<p>On maintenance efficiency:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited as long as the observatory is not fully operational <p>On modal shift:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The alerting system was very attractive for IWW users, it has a great impact Re-routing does not have impact yet, as it

				is very difficult to get data from railway. It is considered useful but attracts concerns: if a cargo leaves IWW, it usually never comes back to it
		Digital Twin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The framework of DT locks and DT buoys has been implemented, but the lack of data impede real predictions 	Impact on IWW reliability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Once filled with the sufficient data, the impact is considered high to help manage IWW infrastructure Collection of data and the correct training of the local teams seem however an issue
		Acoustic Emission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The system detects microcracks, but no results about the lock inspected has been received yet For now, no predictive maintenance as it lacks data to compare 	Impacts on maintenance efficiency: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Impact: especially thanks to the possibility of continuous use without the need of human presence Need of more details of the exact nature of the malfunctions detected to evaluate more precisely the impact To reach greater impact, predictive maintenance needs to be functioning

2.1. Main observation of the BMs, GMs and implementation plan in the French pilot

The French pilot applied the CRISTAL Living Lab (LL) governance framework within an already mature and institutionalized IWT system. Unlike the other pilots, the French pilot did not create new LL events. Instead, CRISTAL activities were strategically intergraded into VNF’s existing stakeholder governance structures. This approach maximalized participation, ensured continuity, and allowed technology validation to take place in real operational contexts on the Seine and Moselle corridors.

The French LL was designed to achieve three objectives:

- enabling technology providers to verify that their solutions align with user needs,

- ensuring transparency from the infrastructure manager toward end-users, and
- providing users with a platform to express challenges and expectations.

Three dedicated events were organised between October 2024 and April 2025 within established forums such as the Comité National des Usagers, the VNF engineers committee, and maintenance roundtables. These sessions used participatory tools, such as Miro boards and structured group discussions, to collect systematic feedback from freight operators, leisure users, public authorities, engineers, and maintenance staff.

This integration into VNF's regular governance cycle proved to be a major strength, offering stable institutional ownership and efficient stakeholder access. However, it also imposed limitations: CRISTAL activities needed to fit pre-existing agendas, and since several technologies were not yet fully developed, VNF presented them as functioning prototypes to allow for meaningful feedback. To manage these challenges, VNF developed a coherent methodology involving interviews with technology providers, the preparation of tailored question sets for each event, and structured 30-minute modules per technology.

Stakeholders contributed extensive insights on the technologies under review. For the Synchronodal Corridor Management System (SCMS), users emphasised the importance of real-time alerts, interoperability with systems such as EurIS and PC-Navigo, and interfaces adapted to freight and leisure users. For the CEDRE tool, operators saw potential to reduce administrative burdens and transport costs but identified concerns around data confidentiality, interoperability, and the need for differentiated interfaces. Technical staff provided detailed input on Acoustic Emission (AE) planning, and enhanced monitoring of locks, bridges, and hydraulic structures. They also raised concerns regarding installation time, noise, interference, maintenance, and diagnostic complexity. The Digital Twin (DT) concept was generally well received as a tool for hydraulic network management and predictive analysis, though stakeholders stressed the need for substantial historical data and clearer added value compared to existing Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition systems. Across technologies, the modular combination of Digital Twin, AE, and SIR was seen as particularly promising.

The Living Lab process did not lead to pilot-specific updates of business or governance models. However, the feedback collected helped refine the generic models, particularly in relation to user value, system integration requirements, operability, and economic feasibility. Ultimately, the French LL's greatest impact lies in raising awareness, stimulating interest in CRISTAL technologies, and fostering a more collaborative culture around innovation within VNF. It also enabled the identification of concrete use cases where AE, SIR, and DTs could be deployed in future phases, marking an important step toward the practical implementation of CRISTAL innovations in French IWT governance.

2.2. Specific consideration for the French pilot

Here, the output of the MIRO workshop will be discussed. The original MIRO board can be found in annex 1.

Experience in the French pilot showed that progress is fastest when development proceeds step by step from the bottom up. When corridor-wide data proved unattainable, it is better to shift to specific assets or market segments and still secured usable results. Physical infrastructure was found to be in better condition than expected and therefore capable of supporting additional traffic, if operators receive

adequate motivation and incentives. Stakeholder awareness can be raised effectively through existing meetings. IWW managers are interested and willing to adopt digital technologies that promise business improvement, but bureaucratic barriers due to the large size of organisation remains a barrier.

The pilot was very successful in engaging businesses, and VNF is creating a dedicated non-invasive-monitoring team, which will amplify CRISTAL's impact. Many VNF assets require precisely the kind of non-invasive investigation demonstrated, paving the way for further projects on this kind of technology.

The pilot was also confronted with challenges. The technical maturity of inland-waterway solutions lags that of road and rail, which is both a limitation and an opportunity for development. Asset condition varies, funding for upgrades is limited and rail cannot be used as an immediate alternative during river disruptions because it demands a year of advance planning. Infrastructure management practices can be very artisanal, data retrieval from EURIS is less seamless than hoped, expertise is scattered across departments and data are sometimes incomplete, badly formatted or not harmonised. These factors, together with low digitalisation and uneven departmental interest, slow implementation.

Overall, the pilot aims to attract additional cargo that can shift to inland waterways with VNF acting as facilitator and to determine how best implement CRISTAL technologies. Key risks are the difficulty of integrating CRISTAL outputs with existing systems identified during the living-lab sessions and the possibility that the developed technologies will not be implemented beyond the pilot phase. Some of the minor challenges that were encountered, while working on the integration of EuRIS datasets into the SCMS, the CERTH software development team, are:

- The data provided by EuRIS are indeed sometimes badly formatted and incomplete. The most concrete example would be the Notices to Skippers validity dates that have weird dates like 0001-01-01 and 9999-12-31, meaning that these kinds of dates require additional manual handling in the backend code of the SCMS both for saving data in the platform's database and for further processing like route planning or extracting analytics and calculating KPIs.
- In case someone wants to hit an authorized API, of course they would need to check out the Swagger documentation page. But most times it is not directly evident if an API is authorized or not, for example, it was found that the authorized APIs contain the 401 HTTP status code in the documentation that's kind of hidden and doesn't stand out visually for the developers to see.
- The emulated ArcGIS APIs can be queried to contain relevant data only for a specific geographical bounding box, that, after it is applied as a filter, the returned data may have data from countries that would not participate in the CRISTAL project, so they would have to be filtered out by building specific mechanisms for that. An example of this case would be that in the SCMS the query for a geographical bounding box that contains Notices to Skippers mostly from France but also contains NtS for Germany and Belgium so these must be filtered out, adding extra development time.

The listed examples are not necessarily deemed problematic, but instead as areas where some improvement could be made to further uptake of the SCMS.

2.3. FR pilot conclusions

The French pilot demonstrated that CRISTAL technologies can meaningfully support digitalisation, monitoring, and operational decision-making within an early mature inland waterway governance system. By embedding the Living Lab activities into VNF's existing stakeholder structures, the pilot achieved strong engagement, high-quality feedback, and efficient integration into real operational contexts. Several technologies, such as CEDRE, Fluv'IOTe, SIR, and the SCMS alert system, showed clear potential for strengthening safety, data reliability, and user-oriented services. Others, including Smart Buoys, Digital Twins, and Acoustic Emission monitoring, highlighted important technical limitations that must be resolved before large-scale roll-out, particularly the need for better datasets, stronger interoperability, and more advanced machine-learning models.

The governance process confirmed that the combination of Digital Twins, AE, and SIR technologies is strategically relevant for VNF, and that incremental, bottom-up deployment is the most effective pathway for innovation adoption. At the same time, the pilot underscored structural constraints within the French IWT sector: bureaucratic rigidity, fragmented data systems, uneven digital maturity, and challenges in integrating CRISTAL tools with legacy platform. Nevertheless, the pilot triggered concrete organisational developments, notably the creation of a dedicated non-invasive monitoring team, and helped to identify clear use cases for future implementation.

Overall, the French pilot validated the **usefulness of CRISTAL technologies** while also revealing the practical conditions required for successful deployment. It strengthened collaboration within VNF, increased stakeholder awareness, and laid the groundwork for targeted future investments. The key challenge moving forward will be ensuring that the momentum generated through CRISTAL continues beyond the project, allowing the technologies to evolve from prototype demonstrations into fully integrated operational tools within the French inland waterway system.

3. Lessons learnt from the Italian pilot

Within the Italian pilot, several CRISTAL and pilot-specific technologies were tested under laboratory and real-environment conditions along the Po River and the Fissero–Tartaro–Canalbianco network. The insights gained from these tests are summarized in the section. Table 4 summarizes the technologies in this pilot.

Fiber Optic Sensors (FOS) developed by ENEA were tested in laboratory settings to explore their capacity to measure the weight and volume of sediment accumulation in shallow sections of the riverbed. Using Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors embedded in a weighing pad, dry-, tank-, and pool-tests demonstrated that the system can reliably detect changes in load corresponding to debris build-up. Although not yet deployed in the right place, the technology shows strong potential to support real-time monitoring of sediment dunes, enabling better dredging planning, reducing survey costs, and improving navigational safety.

Acoustic Emission (AE) monitoring, applied to the Conca di Baricetta lock gate, provided a high level of accuracy in detecting structural anomalies. The system distinguished clearly between normal operation, mechanical impacts, and high-frequency ultrasonic excitations, showing orders-of-magnitude differences in key signal components. This validates AE as a powerful early-warning tool for lock maintenance, with the potential to support predictive maintenance once a larger reference database becomes available. The technology can significantly reduce manual inspections and enhance infrastructure reliability.

The Digital Twin (DT), developed by Fraunhofer, delivered short-term (up to 14 days) water-level and navigability forecasts based on hydrological and meteorological data monitoring discharge and water depth along the Po River. The DT was tested using machine-learning models, including Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Gated Recurrent Units (GRU), and Long Short-Term Net (LSTNet). The DT achieved high accuracy in predicting water depths, with navigability classification exceeding 95% reliability. A dedicated dashboard allows users to visualize critical reaches, vessel-class restrictions, and trends. Although sedimentation data remain limited, the DT has already demonstrated strong potential to improve voyage planning and reduce uncertainty for barge operators.

The Synchronodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) integrates alerts from DT forecasts, AE monitoring, AIPO Notices to Skippers, and user-defined filters to support operational decisions. All functionalities (early detection of disruptions, route impact assessment, alternative mode routing, and corridor observatory KPIs) were successfully tested using simulated data. The Po River instance includes a Smart-Bulletin dashboard offering forecasted navigability maps up to two weeks in advance. The alerting functions operated as expected, though full real-data integration will be finalized at the end of the project. SCMS is the first tool to consolidate all operational and forecasted information for inland waterways in a single platform.

The Navigability Conditions Prediction Model and Smart Bulletin (AIPO, ENEA) combine a statistical probability model with a machine-learning model to produce daily and ten-day navigability forecasts, section by section, for different vessel drafts. The Smart Bulletin aggregates this into color-coded outputs and feeds data into the SCMS. Model validation showed strong accuracy, especially in site-specific configurations where several reaches achieved perfect detection (POD = 1.0). This represents a significant step forward from the current Notice to Skippers system, which only provides measured depths without forecasts.

Cold Ironing, carried out as a feasibility study by Infrastrutture Venete, explored the system-wide deployment of shore-power infrastructure along the Po-Brondolo and Fissero–Tartaro–Canalbiano waterways. While no field test has yet been conducted, detailed engineering designs were completed for multiple landing points, defining phased implementation scenarios. Expected impacts include significant reductions in NO_x, PM, and CO₂ emissions during mooring operations and improved readiness for hybrid-electric vessels. The study highlights the environmental and strategic value of shore power, although implementation requires further investment.

Table 4: Technologies in the Italian pilot, source: Cristal D7.2

Technology	Use	Results	Impacts
Fiber Optic Sensors (FOS)	Continuous monitoring of sediment accumulation in shallow sections.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dry, tank, and pool tests successfully validated weighing-pad concept. • The weighing-pad system reliably detected weight changes corresponding to debris accumulation. • Temperature variations were compensated; sensors worked under water. • Not yet deployed in the river but technically validated. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High potential to improve planning of dredging operations. • Could reduce maintenance costs and improve safety of navigation. • Provides new data for Digital Twin and forecasting models.
Acoustic Emission (AE) Monitoring	Detect early structural anomalies on lock gates (e.g., Conca di Baricetta).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear distinction between normal operation and simulated failures. • 100% success in detecting abnormal acoustic signatures. • Differentiated failure types (impact vs. ultrasonic damage). • Reliable baseline created for future predictive maintenance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhances maintenance efficiency and lock reliability. • Allows early failure detection, reducing risk of sudden breakdowns. • Decreases need for manual inspections.
Digital Twin (DT)	Forecast water levels and navigability up to 14 days ahead.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Machine-learning models (LSTM, GRU, LSTNet) tested; LSTNet performed best. • Navigability classifications >95% accurate. • User-friendly dashboard showing critical sections and trends. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong improvement in voyage planning. • Helps operators anticipate low-water bottlenecks. • Supports multimodal and port coordination.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sedimentation data still limited, reducing long-term accuracy. 	
Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)	Provide alerts, route analysis, multimodal alternatives, and corridor KPIs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All functionalities tested successfully using simulated river data. • Smart Bulletin integrated into the dashboard. • API communication with AIPo validated. • Real data integration ongoing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improves operational visibility for IWW transport. • Supports disruption management and multimodal rerouting. • Key enabler for higher reliability and modal shift.
Navigability Prediction Model & Smart Bulletin	Daily and 10-day navigability forecasts, color-coded per river section and vessel draft.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical and ML models validated, site-specific performance extremely strong. • Several reaches achieved perfect detection (Probability of Detection (POD) = 1.0). • Smart Bulletin produced and integrated into SCMS. • Replaces static Notices to Skippers with predictive information. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Major increase in planning reliability for operators. • Supports safer, more predictable navigation. • Potential for adoption across the entire Po system.
Cold Ironing	Design shore-power infrastructure to reduce emissions during mooring operations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full feasibility analysis and engineering design completed. • Multi-phase deployment plan developed for numerous landing points. • No field test yet (only planning and cost assessment). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expected large reduction in NO_x, PM, and CO₂ emissions at mooring. • Prepares the system for electric/hybrid vessel uptake. • Strong potential for environmental improvements.

3.1. Main observation of the BMs, GMs and implementation plan in the Italian pilot

The Italian pilot applied the CRISTAL Living Lab (LL) governance framework to the Padano-Veneto IWT system, a corridor spanning the Po River, its connected canals, and the Fissero-Tartaro-Canal Bianco network. This region represents a strategically important but underutilized transport corridor, historically hindered by fragmented governance, limited infrastructure investment, and weak modal integration. The Italian Living Lab was therefore conceived as both a technological validation environment and a

governance rebuilding exercise aimed at restoring coordination and shared long-term vision among key actors.

The LL implemented by SOGESCA in collaboration with Unioncamere, Uniontransporti, AIPo, Infrastrutture Venete, and ENEA, and was structured around two complementary cycles: a Governance Cycle focused on institutional cooperation, and a Technology Cycle dedicated to validating CRISTAL innovations (SCMS, FOS, AE, Smart Bulletins, and Cold Ironing feasibility). Using ENoLL principles, the LL relied on extensive stakeholder mapping, identification of gate actors, and iterative participatory methods (workshops, Miro boards, visual canvases, and feedback sessions), to gather inputs from public authorities, users' associations, logistics operators, manufacturers, and infrastructure managers.

A core strength of the Italian pilot was its ability to reactivate dialogue within a sector characterized by institutional silos. Six governance workshops enabled stakeholders to jointly identify systemic issues such as overlapping mandates, inconsistent maintenance responsibilities, dredging coordination, infrastructure accessibility, and insufficient national-level visibility for inland navigation. Through these exchanges, the LL facilitated the co-creation of shared priorities and actionable solutions, helping rebuild trust and a collaborative mindset among actors who rarely interact in a structured setting.

Parallel technology sessions allowed partners to present CRISTAL tools and collect qualitative assessments from relevant user groups. Stakeholders provide feedback on the applicability, perceived benefits, and potential obstacles associated with each technology. These insights informed internal refinement of the business and governance models for the SCMS, DT, and sensor systems, although no major Italy-specific modifications were required.

One of the most significant outputs of the Italian LL was the co-creation of the Manifesto for the Sustainable Development of the Padano-Veneto IWT System, endorsed by over 35 stakeholders. The Manifesto compiles a shared list of problems, proposed solutions, and responsible authorities across themes such as port accessibility, lock maintenance, dredging, mooring services, and hydrometric information. Its strength lies in its collective authorship: for the first time, daily operational challenges were openly articulated from the perspective of users, public administrators, and infrastructure managers. The document became a central advocacy tool, formally presented to the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport in Rome in March 2025 and used to initiate dialogue around incentives and investment needs during the final LL event in Mantua.

The LL process also generated renewed political attention for IWT in Italy. Engagement with the Ministry helped highlight long-standing issues and created a reference group for future national discussions. Stakeholders expressed that they felt heard, strengthening collective motivation and improving the legitimacy of the sector's demands. The final event in Mantua consolidated these achievements by facilitating direct exchanges between ministry representatives and local operators on critical topics such as funding and regulatory incentives.

Overall, the Italian pilot demonstrated the transformative potential of the LL methodology in a context marked by governance fragmentation. Through participatory cycles, the LL helped build a shared vision, validate CRISTAL technologies, and produce a stakeholder-backed framework for a long-term development. Its legacy includes stringer stakeholder cohesion, increased institutional visibility for the IWT system, and a structured roadmap, embodied in the Manifesto, to guide future governance and investment efforts in the Padano-Veneto waterways.

3.2. Specific consideration for the Italian pilot

Here, the output of the MIRO workshop within IT pilot will be discussed. The original MIRO board can be found in Annex 2.

In the Italian pilot, the consortium discovered that digital systems are not the priority for stakeholders. Effective coordination and collaboration across the IWW ecosystem are the basis of driving change. The pilot confirmed that IWW transport is not universally competitive for every type of cargo and highlighted the importance of harmonising regulations between waterways, roads and rail to enable seamless, multimodal logistics chains. Stakeholder interest in developing the network is genuine, yet the high capital cost of infrastructure upgrades continues to limit momentum. Any expansion of the IWW must therefore be synchronised with wider territorial planning, and the development ancillary services is indispensable. Perhaps most importantly, the team saw that a strong sense of shared mission and sound organisational structures will outperform pure digitalisation efforts.

Although Italy's inland waterways represent a relatively small network, the pilot saw a dedicated group of people with technical and operational skills who are highly skilled and believe in the development of IWW. They also saw a high willingness for stakeholder cooperation, and a ministry-backed request to create a formal working group on new governmental incentives. The creation of a collective "Manifesto" for IWW development, coupled with support from public authorities, has already begun to accelerate progress.

Several structural obstacles remain. Stakeholders remain reluctant to shift cargo to IWWs, largely because of lingering doubts about service reliability and limited backing by authorities. The absence of fixed inland routes as well as the lack of rail connections at river ports makes synchronicity difficult to implement. Recruiting specialised professionals is challenging, and the current policy of offering waterways free of charge does not necessarily translate into a competitive advantage as it can obscure the true value of the service and stifle investment. Moreover, because the network serves only a small portion of the country (albeit a highly industrialised one), it struggles to secure nationwide attention and resources.

In the future the pilot hopes to pinpoint specific technologies that could unlock the latent capacity of Italy's rivers. A parallel objective is to broaden national awareness of IWW capabilities so that inland shipping can assume a more prominent role within Italy's freight corridors.

Finally, the pilot underscored the vulnerability of the network to climate variability. Low-water periods, floods and other extreme events threaten both operational continuity and infrastructure integrity, reinforcing the need for resilient design and adaptive management strategies.

3.3. IT pilot conclusions

The Italian pilot case demonstrated that the CRISTAL technologies and LL approach can play an important role in revitalising an IWT system that has long been hindered by fragmentation, limited investment, and weak institutional coordination. While the tested technologies (FOS, AE, DT, SCMS, Smart Bulletins, and Cold Ironing, each delivered valuable insights, their broader impact was magnified by the governance-oriented approach adopted in the Padano-Veneto corridor. Through extensive stakeholder engagement and parallel governance and technology cycles, the pilot succeeded in reactivating dialogue among actors who had previously operated in isolation, creating new opportunities for collaboration, problem-solving, and long-term planning.

Technologically, the Italian pilot confirmed the strong potential of CRISTAL innovations to improve the reliability, safety, and predictability of inland navigation. Laboratory and field testing validated the relevance of FOS for sediment monitoring, AE for non-invasive structural diagnostics, and the DT and Smart Bulletin for forecasting navigability conditions, an issue of particular importance on the Po River. SCMS was shown to be a powerful integrative platform capable of consolidating operational and forecast information, although full deployment will require stronger data flows and operational integration. Cold Ironing, while still in a feasibility phase, highlighted an important pathway for decarbonising IWT infrastructure. Together, these technologies form a complementary suite of tools capable of addressing many of the systemic challenges identified by operators and authorities.

The governance dimension of the pilot proved equally significant. The creation of the Manifesto for the sustainable development of the Padano-Veneto IWT system marked a milestone in stakeholder cooperation, articulating shared priorities and concrete actions across infrastructure maintenance, operational coordination, regulatory reforms, and incentive schemes. Its presentation to the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport (alongside the final LL event in Mantua) helped bring national visibility to a corridor that often suffers from limited political attention. Stakeholders expressed renewed motivation, a stronger sense of collective purpose, and confidence that coordinated governance reforms are both necessary and achievable.

At the same time, the pilot exposed persistent structural barriers: limited competitiveness of IWW for certain cargo types, the absence of reliable multimodal connections at river ports, inadequate national-level recognition, and significant capital needs for upgrading infrastructure. Stakeholders also noted that the sector's resilience is increasingly threatened by climate variability, underscoring the importance of predictive tools and adaptive management. These challenges reinforce the need for a combined strategy that integrates technological innovation with institutional strengthening, regulatory reforms, and targeted investment.

Overall, the Italian pilot demonstrated the transformative potential of CRISTAL when applied in a complex and fragmented inland navigation ecosystem. By validating new technologies, strengthening stakeholder cooperation, and establishing a shared roadmap for future development, the pilot laid the foundation for a more reliable, sustainable, and competitive IWT system in Northern Italy. Sustaining this momentum will be essential to ensure that the progress achieved through CRISTAL evolves into long-term structural change.

4. Lessons learnt from the Polish pilot

With the Polish pilot, the CRISTAL technologies were introduced, demonstrated, and evaluated in relation to the operational realities of the Vistula River. Unlike the Italian and French pilots, where several tools were tested in the field, the Polish pilot operated within a context characterized by limited waterway infrastructure, rapidly fluctuating hydrological conditions, and a lack of long-term monitoring data. As a result, much of the work focused on assessing applicability, validating relevance through stakeholder engagement, and analyzing operational constraints through pilot voyages carried out by VAN Cargo S.A. The insights gained from these activities are summarized below. Table 5 provides an overview of the solutions considered within the Polish pilot.

Fiber Optic Sensors (FOS) developed by ENEA were not deployed in Poland due to the absence of robust infrastructure for installing riverbed monitoring equipment. However, their functionality was demonstrated and discussed with Polish stakeholders. Given the Vistula's substantial shallow-water constraints and dynamic sedimentation patterns, FOS technology was widely recognized as highly relevant for improving future navigability. Stakeholders highlighted its potential to support continuous monitoring of sediment dunes, reduce uncertainty for operators, and enable more efficient dredging strategies once adequate installation conditions are available.

Acoustic Emission (AE) monitoring, successfully applied in Italy, could not be tested on the Vistula River as the relevant sections lack operational locks comparable to those in the other pilots. Nevertheless, demonstrations of the AE results from Italy allowed Polish infrastructure managers to appreciate its usefulness for early detection of structural anomalies in gates and hydraulic structures. As Poland continues to modernize key elements of its inland waterway infrastructure, particularly around critical nodes such as Włocławek, the AE system was identified as an important tool for future maintenance planning and risk mitigation.

The Digital Twin (DT) was presented as a forecasting framework that could significantly improve operational planning on the Vistula. In Poland, however, a Digital Twin could not yet be developed because long-term water-depth, sedimentation, and discharge datasets are fragmented or unavailable. Despite this limitation, stakeholders expressed strong interest in the predictive capabilities demonstrated in the Italian pilot, especially given the rapid and unpredictable water-level changes that affect Vistula navigation. The pilot highlighted that the main barrier to DT deployment in Poland is data availability rather than technological readiness.

The Synchronodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) was demonstrated to Polish stakeholders using simulated Vistula data. The platform's functionality (integrating alerts, visualizing disruptions, assessing route feasibility, and offering alternative multimodal options) was well received. However, stakeholders emphasized that SCMS can only reach its full potential once Poland strengthens hydrological monitoring and provides reliable navigability inputs. Nevertheless, the system was recognized as a promising tool for improving communication, operational decision-making, and long-term corridor management across Poland's transport network.

The Navigability Conditions Prediction Model and Smart Bulletin, successfully implemented in Italy, could not be operationalized in Poland due to the lack of long-term depth and discharge time series required for statistical calibration. However, the concept was viewed as highly valuable. The pilot voyages strongly confirmed the need for a predictive navigability tool: several river sections showed water depths as low as 30–40 cm, severely restricting the maneuverability of the vessel. Stakeholders indicated that a Smart

Bulletin offering multi-day navigability forecasts could be transformative for both freight and tourism operations once data availability improves.

Cold Ironing was not part of the Polish technological tests, but the concept was presented within broader discussions on decarbonization and sustainable tourism. For urban river sections in Warsaw, Gdańsk, and Bydgoszcz, shore-power infrastructure was considered highly relevant for reducing emissions from leisure and passenger vessels. Although outside the immediate scope of the pilot, cold ironing aligns with Poland's longer-term sustainability goals.

Overall, the Polish pilot confirmed the strong relevance of CRISTAL technologies for improving the reliability, safety, and sustainability of inland waterway transport in Poland. While limited by infrastructure and data constraints, the pilot generated valuable insights into the operational challenges of the Vistula and highlighted clear priorities for future development. Stakeholders expressed consistent interest in adopting predictive tools, monitoring systems, and corridor-management solutions, provided that the underlying hydrological and infrastructural prerequisites can be strengthened. The Polish pilot therefore establishes an important foundation for future IWT innovation and investment in Poland.

Table 5: Technologies in the Polish pilot, source: Cristal D9.2

Technology	Use	Results	Impacts
Fiber Optic Sensors (FOS)	Intended for continuous monitoring of sediment accumulation and shallow areas to assess navigability conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>FOS was not deployed in Poland</u> due to infrastructural constraints, but the technology was presented and discussed with Polish stakeholders. • Stakeholders confirmed relevance for the Vistula's shallow-water challenges. • Anticipated as a valuable addition to long-term sediment and riverbed monitoring. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expected to support more efficient dredging planning. • Could significantly improve navigability reliability in shallow sections. • Reinforces the need for integration of Polish river data into future DT models.
Acoustic Emission (AE) Monitoring	Monitoring structural health of locks and hydraulic structures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As the Vistula has very few operational locks in the tested sections, AE was not deployed in the field. • Stakeholders saw strong potential for AE in future modernization of Polish hydraulic structures (e.g., Włocławek barrage). • Demonstrations and data from Italy and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Useful for long-term infrastructure planning and future lock upgrades. • Seen as essential for increasing safety and reliability as the Polish IWW network develops. • Helps raise awareness about structural monitoring needs in Poland.

		France were used to validate the relevance.	
Digital Twin (DT)	Forecasting water levels, navigability, and providing decision support for planning.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DT was demonstrated conceptually; no operational Polish DT is available yet due to lack of historical depth/discharge datasets. Stakeholders expressed strong interest in DT functionalities for predicting low-water events, which severely limit navigation on the Vistula. The Polish pilot identified data availability as the main barrier for implementation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High potential to improve voyage planning and forecasting once data gaps are addressed. Could reduce navigational uncertainty and enable seasonal route optimization. This pilot highlighted the need for systematic hydrological data collection.
Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)	Providing alerts, routing information, and multimodal alternatives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SCMS was demonstrated using simulated data for the Vistula. Stakeholders valued the corridor-wide view and multimodal routing but stressed that SCMS requires reliable underlying hydrological inputs. Operators noted high potential for predicting disruptions and rerouting via rail/road. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Seen as a strategic tool for future integration of inland waterways into multimodal corridors. Potentially increases reliability once the Vistula’s hydrological forecasting improves. Demonstrated the importance of data standardization in Poland.
Navigability Prediction Model & Smart Bulletin	Forecasting daily and medium-term navigability conditions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not fully implementable in Poland due to lack of long-term water depth and sedimentation databases. Stakeholders confirmed that such a system is urgently needed for the Vistula, where water levels can change drastically within hours. Pilot voyages confirmed the extent of low-water bottlenecks (several 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Once data availability improves, the Smart Bulletin is expected to become transformational for planning. Would support safer operations, seasonal tourism management, and freight planning. Enables a shift from reactive to proactive river management.

		shallow sections as low as 30–40 cm).	
Cold Ironing	Providing shore-side electrical power to reduce emissions during mooring.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not part of the Polish RP activities (no port infrastructure modernization under CRISTAL). • Discussed with stakeholders as part of broader decarbonisation strategies for Warsaw and Gdańsk river tourism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Considered relevant for future development of passenger and tourist traffic along the Vistula. • Supports long-term green transition objectives of Polish ports.
Pilot Voyages (VAN Cargo S.A.)	Four cargo voyages were executed to assess real-life navigability and operational constraints.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple critical shallow-water sections observed, limiting draft to as little as 30–40 cm. • Navigation often required maneuvering in the navigable thread rather than using the full fairway. • Unpredictable conditions significantly affect commercial viability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrated the urgent need for accurate water-level monitoring and forecasting systems. • Validated the potential utility of DT, SCMS, and Smart Bulletin tools even before deployment.

4.1. Main observation of the BMs, GMs and implementation plan in the Polish pilot

The Polish pilot represents the third and last application of the CRISTAL Living Lab (LL) governance framework, focusing on the Vistula River and the broader inland waterway transport (IWT) system in Poland. Compared to Italy and France, the Polish LL is at an earlier stage of development, primarily due to the specific contextual challenges of the Vistula River, including infrastructural limitations, seasonal variability, and complex stakeholder coordination. Despite this, it has already established a strong foundation for participatory governance, stakeholder engagement, and technology validation. The pilot is coordinated by the University of Gdańsk and aims to assess the relevance and feasibility of CRISTAL innovations within a river system marked by infrastructural challenges, seasonal variability, and substantial development potential.

The LL was launched on 14 April 2025 at the University of Gdańsk, bringing together more than 20 stakeholders from logistics companies, port authorities, inland navigation operators, public institutions, technology providers, and academic. The event served two purposes: to evaluate the outcomes of four pilot voyages carried out under CRISTAL and to initiate a structured dialogue on the socio-economic potential of revitalizing IWT in Poland. The meeting also raised awareness about the role of IWT in the EU's green transition, highlighting both opportunities and systemic barriers.

The first part of the LL focused on presenting research findings from Deliverable 9.3: Socio Economic Research and recommendations, which examined public and stakeholder perceptions of the Vistula River. Surveys conducted with the public, transport-sector stakeholders, and tourism professionals revealed strong overall support for using the river for freight, tourism, and recreation. Respondents emphasized sustainability benefits, reduced road congestion, and regional development potential. However, they also expressed concerns related to ecological impacts on the river ecosystem (including water quality, biodiversity, and riverbank habitats), insufficient infrastructure, and low water levels. The research also underscored the need for clear national leadership, with most stakeholders expecting centralized responsibility and long-term investment planning from government institutions.

The second phase of the event was dedicated to feedback on CRISTAL technologies, including SCMS, sensor-based systems, and digital tools. Stakeholders saw technological integration as a potentially powerful enabler of more reliable operations, particularly in managing disruptions caused by variable river depth or extreme weather. Participants believed a unified technological layer across road, rail, and waterborne transport could significantly improve multimodal coordination. At the same time, they emphasized that technology alone cannot compensate for structural deficiencies: without modernized infrastructure, consistent water levels, and regulatory reform, digital tools would have limited impact. Feedback on technology-related benefits, such as risk reduction, navigation support, and improved data flow, was cautiously optimistic but tempered by a recognition that governance and investment must evolve in parallel.

The third component of the LL was an open stakeholder discussion, anchored in the practical experiences from the pilot voyages conducted by VAN Cargo S.A. Low water levels, inadequate depth, and infrastructural bottlenecks were identified as primary operational obstacles. Additional concerns included encroachment of residential developments on port and logistics zones, institutional fragmentation, and non-governmental organisation (NGO) pressures affecting project permitting, and the instability of short-term governmental budgeting cycles. The dialogue highlighted that IWT development in Poland is not hindered by a lack of interest or potential, but by an absence of cohesive strategy, long-term financing, and coordinated governance across ministries and agencies.

Initial adaptations of the CRISTAL governance and business models focused on aligning them with Poland's regulatory and institutional structures. Early discussions emphasized multi-level coordination between national authorities, regional governments, and waterway managers, as well as the potential for public-private partnerships around technologies such as SCMS and sensor-based monitoring systems. While no pilot-specific updates to the models were introduced at this stage, the LL laid the groundwork for future tailoring by identifying decision-making gaps, investment needs, and areas where CRISTAL tools could support planning and operational reliability.

Overall, the Polish LL demonstrated strong interest in the future development of IWT and confirmed the transferability of the CRISTAL framework to the Polish context. It highlighted both the significant potential of IWT as a sustainable transport mode and the substantial challenges that must be addressed, namely infrastructural modernization, stable financing, ecological safeguards, and coherent policy leadership. The LL has initiated an essential dialogue that positions the Polish pilot for deeper stakeholder engagement and more advanced governance and technology integration in the next years after project completion.

4.2. Specific consideration for the Polish pilot

Here, the output of the MIRO workshop within PL pilots will be discussed. The original MIRO board can be found in Annex 3.

Within the Polish pilot, the consortium has found the political environment to be constructive. National authorities are willing to discuss inland-waterway-transport (IWT) development, yet they consistently request solid, market-based evidence before committing future capital. This is sensible, because the existing waterway infrastructure is inadequate and cannot be modernised quickly. Any large-scale upgrade will require a phased, economically justified programme rather than a rapid overhaul. This overall could be supported for instance by the CEF program.

Two findings stood out:

- First, real-time monitoring revealed that water levels can fall even lower than historical records suggested, occasionally exposing the riverbed.
- Second, the pilot achieved an unexpectedly high response rate to stakeholder surveys, signalling that industry, academia and local communities are ready and willing to engage in shaping Poland's IWT agenda.

Operational challenges are large. Low water, ageing infrastructure and the fragmentation of responsibility across multiple authorities collectively undermine reliability. These physical and institutional constraints make it difficult to convince shippers to divert cargo to rivers, even though the broader business community is generally supportive of the IWT concept. Digitalisation has only just begun, so data availability and system integration are still limited.

In the future the team hopes to translate the pilot's technical and organisational lessons into Poland's national IWT development strategy. Priority topics include quantifying market demand, specifying affordable infrastructure packages and defining a realistic timeline for full digital integration especially considering the encouraging stakeholder engagement evidenced by the survey results.

Risks largely mirror the challenges already listed: persistently low water levels, unplanned lock closures, ice events and administrative bottlenecks. In addition, the prospect of pushing barges into new areas of operation introduces fresh regulatory and safety uncertainties that will need careful management.

4.3. PL pilot conclusions

The Polish pilot confirmed that the CRISTAL technologies are highly relevant for the Vistula River but also showed that their deployment is constrained by fundamental infrastructural and data limitations. Pilot voyages and stakeholder discussions revealed severe and increasingly frequent low-water situations, bottlenecks and ageing infrastructure, which together compromised the reliability of IWT. Under these conditions, most tools (FOS, AE, DT, SCMS, Smart Bulletin and Cold Ironing) could not yet be implemented operationally, but were recognised as important components of a future, better-equipped IWT system. The main barrier is therefore not technological readiness, but the absence of modernised infrastructure systematic hydrological monitoring and integrated digital systems.

From a governance perspective, the Polish LL demonstrated long stakeholder interest and a constructive political environment. The launch event in Gdańsk, the high survey response rate and the active participation of public and private actors all indicate that there is a clear appetite to develop IWT, if

investments are guided by solid market evidence and long-term strategic planning. The LL helped to surface key priorities: the need for a coherent national strategy, stable and phased financing, clearer allocation of responsibilities across institutions, and ecological safeguards compatible with river revitalisation.

Overall, the Polish pilot shows that while Poland starts from a less advanced baseline than France and Italy, the CRISTAL governance framework is transferable and valuable in this context. By identifying data gaps, operational constraints and stakeholder expectations, the pilot has laid the groundwork for future tailoring of CRISTAL solutions and for integrating digital tools into Poland's evolving IWT strategy once the necessary infrastructural and institutional prerequisites are in place.

5. Generic lessons learnt from the three case studies

This section summarizes the common insights emerging from the French, Italian, and Polish pilots. While each pilot applied the CRISTAL technologies and LL governance framework in a distinct institutional and hydrological context, several overarching lessons can be identified.

5.1. Generic lessons learnt from the 3 pilots

The three pilots demonstrated that the starting conditions of each waterway system strongly influence the way technologies can be deployed:

- **France** operates within a mature and industrialised IWT system, where digitalisation efforts must align with existing structures and legacy systems. Its challenge is not adoption willingness, but system integration and data harmonisation.
- **Italy** represents a fragmented but highly motivated ecosystem. While institutional coordination is weak, stakeholder engagement is strong. The pilot showed that governance renewal and strategic alignment are prerequisites for technology uptake.
- **Poland** is at an early stage of IWT redevelopment. Severe hydrological constraints and lack of monitoring infrastructure limit immediate deployment. However, stakeholder interest is high, and the pilot laid a foundation for future digitalisation.

Despite these differences, all three pilots recognized the relevance of CRISTAL tools for improving reliability, safety, and planning capacity. Importantly, each pilot identified data availability, interoperability, and institutional coordination as critical factors shaping the success of technological implementation.

5.2. Generic implementation plan

Across all three pilots, the implementation of CRISTAL technologies converged around several shared principles and requirements:

1. **Data first:** the pilots showed that reliable data are necessary and essential for effective use of predictive and monitoring technologies, such as DT and SCMS. Where data is incomplete or unstandardised (FR, IT), or largely absent (PL), implementation is slowed or constrained.
2. **Incremental deployment:** a step-by-step, bottom-up approach (testing specific assets before scaling corridor-wide proved to be most effective. France and Italy demonstrated that piloting at asset level (locks, buoys, sediment points) builds credibility and helps refine tools before broader rollout.
3. **Integration with existing systems:** technologies must align with local systems such as VNF's operational tools, AIPo platforms, or future hydrological networks. Interoperability is a shared requirement across all pilots.
4. **Stakeholder-driven refinement:** Continuous feedback loops, via LL workshops, MIRO boards, and interviews, were crucial for tailoring functionalities, identifying barriers, and validating user priorities.

5. **Institutional anchoring:** technologies gain viability when embedded in organisational structures: integration into VNF’s existing committees (FR), formalised stakeholder coalitions (Manifesto, IT), and early-stage alignment with national authorities (PL). Sustained adoption requires management support, clear roles, and long-term ownership.
6. **Need for complementary governance reform:** all pilots agreed that technologies alone cannot compensate for weak institutional coordination, fragmented responsibilities, or unclear strategic planning. Successful implementation requires parallel improvements in governance, regulation, and investment frameworks.

Across the three studied pilots, these principles manifested not as abstract recommendations but as practical conditions that could help to shape the implementation of innovative technologies. The pilots made clear that technological innovation in inland waterways is only as strong as the foundations on which it rests. Reliable, structured data proved to be the primary enabler—where datasets are robust, tools such as digital twins and supply chain monitoring systems could immediately demonstrate value, whereas in data-poor environments, effort shifted toward establishing the basic informational infrastructure needed for any advanced system to function.

The pilots also showed that complexity can be managed through incremental rollout. Beginning with specific assets allowed technology developers to validate assumptions, adjust system parameters, and build confidence among operators and managers. This bottom-up trajectory helped each corridor adapt technology to real operational constraints rather than imposing one-size-fits-all solutions.

A second recurring theme was the necessity of fitting new tools into existing operational ecosystems. Without interoperability—whether with VNF’s systems (EURIS), AIPo’s information systems, or the Polish systems. Each pilot gravitated toward architectures that complement rather than compete with incumbent systems.

Sustained interaction with stakeholders will play a decisive role in making the technologies usable and relevant. Workshops, feedback boards, and iterative interviews served not just as consultation forums but should also work as co-design mechanisms. This continuous dialogue helped ensure that functionalities aligned with the needs of operators, planners, and industry actors, while also surfacing institutional bottlenecks that technology alone could not resolve.

In all three pilots, the institutional dimension emerged as equally important as the technical one. Embedding the technologies into organizational structures, through existing committees, formalized coalitions, or strategic alignment with national agencies, provided the governance backbone for long-term adoption. Without such anchoring, even well-designed tools risk remaining isolated pilot projects.

Finally, the pilots underlined a critical insight: technical innovation cannot substitute for coherent governance. Fragmented responsibilities, outdated regulatory frameworks, and unclear investment pathways can negate even the most sophisticated systems. For CRISTAL technologies to reach their full potential, their deployment must be accompanied by reforms that strengthen coordination, clarify mandates, and ensure stable resourcing. Only through this dual track—technical integration and governance improvement—can the corridors create resilient, data-driven management models capable of supporting future modal shift and climate resilience ambitions.

5.3. Generic lessons learnt - conclusions

Taken together, the pilots show that the success of CRISTAL technologies hinges on far more than the performance of the tools themselves. Their value emerges when reliable data, operational alignment, and interdisciplinary collaboration come together to support informed decision-making. When these conditions are in place, the technologies can significantly strengthen planning, enhance operational resilience, and enable a more predictive and coordinated approach to managing inland waterways. The pilots demonstrated that even in very different institutional contexts, a consistent set of enablers drives progress and ensures that innovation translates into practical benefits for waterway authorities, operators, and users.

Looking ahead, the convergence of lessons across France, Italy, and Poland offers a roadmap for other corridors considering similar modernization paths. A pragmatic sequence, data consolidation, incremental deployment, integration with existing systems, and strong governance anchoring, creates the conditions for scalable and durable adoption. Equally, the pilots warn that without parallel governance improvements, technological solutions risk remaining isolated experiments. By combining technical innovation with institutional strengthening, waterway authorities can lay the groundwork for a more reliable, climate-resilient, and interconnected European inland waterway network.

6. General conclusions

Across the three pilots, the CRISTAL project demonstrated that technological innovation can meaningfully enhance the reliability, safety, and planning capacity of inland waterway transport—but only when the right institutional and operational foundations are in place. The pilots showed that while Digital Twins, AE monitoring, FOS, Smart Bulletins, and the Synchromodal Corridor Management System all have strong potential, their actual effectiveness depends on data availability, system interoperability, and the capacity of governance structures to integrate new tools into established workflows.

The assessment of the different pilots showed that different starting conditions shape the pace and trajectory of innovation. France, with its mature IWT system, focused primarily on integrating CRISTAL technologies into existing legacy systems and harmonizing scattered data sources. Italy used the CRISTAL framework as a catalyst to rebuild coordination in a fragmented but highly motivated ecosystem, demonstrating that governance renewal is often a prerequisite for technological adoption. Poland, working within an underdeveloped waterway and limited hydrological data, revealed that infrastructural and monitoring gaps (not stakeholder willingness) are the main barriers to digitalization. Yet in all three countries, stakeholders consistently expressed interest in predictive tools, monitoring systems, and corridor-management platforms, underscoring the relevance of CRISTAL innovations across diverse contexts.

A core lesson emerging from the pilots is that incremental, bottom-up deployment is the most effective path for technology uptake. Starting with specific assets, such as locks, buoys, sediment zones, allowed developers to test assumptions, refine system parameters, and build trust among users. This approach ensured that technological solutions were grounded in real operational conditions rather than theoretical designs, improving usability and speeding up acceptance. At the same time, the project demonstrated that new tools must fit into existing operational ecosystems; without interoperability with established platforms such as VNF's systems, AIPo's data services, or Poland's emerging hydrological networks, technology risks remaining isolated and under-used.

Equally important was the role of stakeholder engagement and structured governance processes. Living Lab methods gave operators, public authorities, and industry actors a meaningful platform to shape technological functionality, identify barriers, and flag institutional constraints. These interactions clarified that technology adoption is inseparable from governance quality. Where leadership is clear, mandates are coherent, and institutional cooperation is strong, innovation progresses more rapidly; where responsibilities are fragmented or strategic planning is weak, progress slows and technologies struggle to achieve impact.

The pilots therefore converge on a clear conclusion: CRISTAL technologies deliver value only when accompanied by stronger governance, improved coordination, and sustained investment in monitoring and data systems. Digital innovation cannot compensate for fragmented responsibilities, outdated regulatory frameworks, or deteriorating infrastructure. Instead, it must be integrated into a broader modernization strategy that includes institutional reform, resourcing, and long-term planning. At the EU level, this implies the need for harmonized regulatory frameworks, cross-border coordination mechanisms, and dedicated funding streams to support digitalization and sustainable development across inland waterways. Such measures would ensure that the benefits observed in individual pilots can be scaled and replicated throughout the European IWT network.

Looking forward, the lessons from France, Italy, and Poland provide a transferable roadmap for other European corridors. The most effective sequence combines:

1. Consolidation of data and monitoring capabilities,
2. Incremental deployment starting from strategic assets,
3. Alignment with existing operational systems, and
4. Strong institutional anchoring supported by participatory governance.

Based on the results of the analysis and on Cryns et al (2025) it can be concluded that there is a decisive influence of strong leadership, whether exercised by public authorities, infrastructure managers, or major industry actors. Where a clear institutional leader is present, as in France and Italy, innovation efforts tend to advance more smoothly: priorities are more coherent, coordination is easier, and stakeholders have a recognized point of reference. By contrast, the Polish pilot illustrates how the absence of a strong guiding actor can slow progress, making it harder to align responsibilities and sustain momentum in developing the IWT sector. Overall, the comparison suggests that when leadership is well established, collaboration improves and innovation spreads more readily, whereas fragmented leadership environments face greater implementation challenges.

Across all three contexts, systematic stakeholder identification and mapping proved essential for understanding the operational, governance, and economic dimensions of IWT, and for addressing the barriers that can impede innovation. A thorough mapping exercise helps ensure that the full range of stakeholder needs is captured and integrated, supporting balanced decision-making and reducing the risk that important perspectives are overlooked. This, in turn, facilitates alignment with broader European goals to reduce CO₂ emissions and strengthen the competitiveness of inland waterways. Clear and proactive communication with stakeholders also plays a preventive role: it helps build trust, reduces resistance when significant reforms or investments such as digitalization, are introduced, and ultimately supports smoother implementation.

If pursued together, these steps can turn pilot-scale innovations into sustained operational improvements, enabling inland waterways to play a larger role in Europe's modal shift and climate-resilience objectives. Ultimately, **the CRISTAL project shows that technology and governance must evolve together**; when they do, the potential for a smarter, more reliable, and more sustainable inland waterway network becomes fully attainable.

7. References

- [1] Cristal D4.2: Development of a generic living lab governance framework
- [2] Cristal D7.2: Italian River Pilot Solutions description, test results and impact assessment
- [3] Cristal D8.2: French RP Solution description, test results and impact assessment
- [4] CristalD9.2: Polish RP Solution description, test results and impact assessment
- [5] Cryns Marie, van Hassel Edwin, Vanelslander Thierry (2025). Stakeholder identification and mapping in peripheral European inland waterway ecosystems. *Journal of Shipping and Trade / Hong Kong Polytechnic University Shipping Research Centre* - ISSN 2364-4575 - 10:1(2025), 11
- [6] Commission Regulation (EU) No 164/2010 of 25 January 2010 on the Technical Specifications for Electronic Ship Reporting in Inland Navigation Referred to in Article 5 of Directive 2005/44/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on Harmonised River Information Services (RIS) on Inland Waterways in the Community, 057 OJ L (2010). <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2010/164/oj>

8. Appendices

Annex 1

Overview of the French Pilot

Lessons already learnt

Unexpected insights or success stories

Challenges encountered (part 1) (institutional, cultural, etc.)

Challenges encountered (part 2)

making really hard to get all the needed information

VNF processes are not only defined by VNF

It is practically impossible today to use rail as an alternative when disruptions occur in rivers because it requires planning 1 year before

The connection & retrieving of information from EURIS is not as effortless as expected

What do you expect/hope to learn in the upcoming months?

More cargo on IWT and VNF as the main facilitator for reinforcing the modal shift

how to effectively implement CRISTAL techs

Perceived risks and threats

the integration of CRISTAL systems with other existing systems (some were quoted in the living lab sessions)

that in the end, the technologies developed by CRISTAL will not really be implemented

Annex 2

Overview of the Italian Pilot

Lessons already learnt

- Lessons already learnt
- Challenges encountered (technical, institutional, cultural, etc.)
- Lack of institutional support and/or change in 2020 due to the lack of resources and the poor support of authorities

Unexpected insights or success stories

What do we still hope/expect to learn in the upcoming months?

What do we still hope/expect to learn in the upcoming months?

Perceived risks and threats

Perceived risks and threats

Italy

Lessons already learnt

Unexpected insights or success stories

Challenges encountered

What do you hope/expect to learn in the upcoming months?

Perceived risks and threats

Annex 3

Overview of the Polish Pilot

Lessons already learnt

Unexpected insights or success stories

The water level can be lower than reported in the past even to the dry bottom events.

The level of survey respondents! CONGRATS!!

Challenges encountered

institutional, cultural, etc.)

Lack of water, insufficient infrastructure, multiple authorities responsible for different elements of the IWW, but quite positive social and business approach to the IWT.

Digitalization is at early stages

Low water levels which become more and more frequent, cancel any effort to attract cargo to rivers (due to lack of reliability)

What do you still hope/expect to learn in the upcoming months?

How to implement gathered experience into the national IWW development strategy

Perceived risks and threats

Actually, the same as challenges - low water levels, unexpected locks closures, ice events, documentation issues, entering new ares of operation (barges at sea).

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